

Prompting or Fine-tuning? Evaluating Relation Classification in Portuguese for Knowledge Graph Construction

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Abstract. This paper explores relation classification as a step toward building structured knowledge graphs from unstructured Portuguese text. We evaluate prompt-based approaches using generative large language models and compare them with a fine-tuned BERT model. Experiments are conducted on a custom relation extraction dataset built by aligning Wikidata triples with sentences from Wikipedia in Portuguese, a lower-resourced language than English. Results show that while prompt-based methods offer flexibility and reasonable performance, fine-tuning yields significantly better results in identifying relation types, an essential aspect for accurate and reliable knowledge graph construction.

Keywords: Relation Classification · Large Language Models · Prompting Strategies · Fine-Tuning · Knowledge Graph Construction

1 Introduction

Relation Classification (RC) is a fundamental subtask of Relation Extraction (RE), concerned with identifying the semantic relationship between two entities mentioned in a text [2]. As a key step in transforming unstructured text into structured representations, RC plays a vital role in the construction and enrichment of Knowledge Graphs (KGs). Correctly identifying the relation between entity pairs directly impacts the accuracy and utility of the resulting graph in downstream applications such as information retrieval, question answering, and recommendation systems [19].

The RC task has traditionally been addressed using supervised learning approaches, where labeled datasets and dedicated classifiers were central to performance [17]. With the advent of pretrained transformer models, particularly BERT [5] and its variants, supervised fine-tuning has continued the dominant paradigm for improving RC accuracy [20].

In recent years, the emergence of generative Large Language Models (LLMs), such as GPT-4 and Llama 3 [1,6], has reshaped the landscape of Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, including RC [16]. Their ability to generalize and perform well in zero or few-shot settings makes them attractive candidates

for building multilingual or domain-adaptable KG pipelines [15]. However, fine-tuned encoder-based models remain a strong alternative, especially in low computational resource settings and when high precision is critical [18].

Although RE and RC have been extensively studied for English, research in other languages, particularly Portuguese, continues to be limited. This is largely due to the scarcity of annotated datasets, adapted models, and language-specific tools [18]. A few prior efforts have explored Portuguese RE using BERT-based models [8,10], but the use of generative LLMs in this context remains largely unexplored.

To address this gap, our study focuses on RC in Portuguese using both prompting strategies with generative LLMs and supervised fine-tuning. Our goal is to evaluate the performance and potential of these approaches within the broader context of KG construction.

2 Methodology

In this work, the RC task is formulated as follows: given a sentence and a pair of mentioned entities (subject and object), the model must identify the correct relation between them from a predefined set. This section describes the dataset, models used, prompting strategies explored, and the fine-tuning setup.

2.1 Dataset

A custom sentence-level dataset was created using a distant supervision approach, where Wikidata¹ triples were aligned with Portuguese Wikipedia² sentences that contain both the subject and object entities. For each instance, the sentence, subject, object, and corresponding relation label are included, as shown in table 1. The dataset covers 18 distinct Wikidata relation types: *author*, *composer*, *director*, *developer*, *father*, *genre*, *headquarters location*, *instance of*, *located in or next to body of water*, *main subject*, *occupation*, *place of birth*, *producer*, *production company*, *religion*, *sport*, *subclass of*, and *taxon rank*. These were selected based on their frequency in the Wikidata triples dump and the number of valid instances generated by our pipeline. The data is divided into 70 training instances and 30 testing instances for each relation type, totaling 1,260 training and 540 testing instances overall.

To reduce distant supervision noise, we applied a Natural Language Inference (NLI) filtering step, inspired by Cabot et al. [3]. A Portuguese NLI model³ was used to verify the entailment between the Wikidata triple (expressed textually) and the corresponding sentence [4]. Only instances with an entailment probability higher than or equal to 95% were retained, ensuring high semantic consistency in the dataset.

We intend to make the dataset publicly available in the near future to support further research in Portuguese RE and distant supervision techniques.

¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/>

² <https://pt.wikipedia.org/>

³ <https://huggingface.co/ruanchaves/mdeberta-v3-base-assin2-entailment>

Sentence: "Na mitologia nórdica, Bestla era uma antiga jotun (mulher gigante), filha de Bolthorn e irmã de Mímir." ⁴
Subject: Bestla / Object: Bolthorn / Relation: pai (father)

Sentence: "Montecristo é uma ilha italiana do arquipélago Toscano (região da Toscana), no mar Tirreno." ⁵
Subject: Montecristo / Object: Mar Tirreno / Relation: banhado por (located in or next to body of water)

Table 1. Example instances from the custom dataset.

2.2 Models

The first category of models in our study is generative LLMs, used in a zero-shot setting through prompt-based inference. These include the full versions of gemma-2-2b-it [14] and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 [7] from Hugging Face⁶, as well as the quantized base versions of gemma-3-27b-it [13] and Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct [9] from Ollama⁷. The second approach focuses on BERTimbau base [11], a Portuguese pretrained encoder based on BERT, which we fine-tuned on our dataset in a supervised setting.

The chosen models represent a range of parameter sizes, enabling both a comparison between prompt-based and fine-tuned approaches, as well as an investigation into how model scale impacts performance.

2.3 Prompting Strategies

Two prompting strategies were designed for the setup: Prompt 1 provides the model with a straightforward task instruction for zero-shot classification, while Prompt 2, building on the structure of Prompt 1, aims to familiarize the model with the possible relation types by offering brief descriptions of each one. Since the task is performed in Portuguese text, both prompts are written in Portuguese (see Appendix A for English translations), and examples are presented in Figures 1 and 2, respectively.

This approach allows evaluating LLMs’ ability to generalize to RC without additional training, providing a more flexible way of operation.

2.4 Model Fine-tuning

For the supervised learning setup, BERTimbau was adapted for RC by adding a linear classification head on top of the encoder, predicting one of the predefined

⁴ "In Norse mythology, Bestla was an ancient jotun (giantess), daughter of Bolthorn and sister of Mímir."

⁵ "Montecristo is an Italian island in the Tuscan Archipelago (Tuscany region), in the Tyrrhenian Sea."

⁶ <https://huggingface.co/>

⁷ <https://ollama.com/>

Analise a seguinte frase:
 "O filme Central do Brasil foi dirigido por Walter Salles."

Identifique qual relação existe entre "Central do Brasil" e "Walter Salles".
 Escolha apenas uma das seguintes relações possíveis: instância de, ocupação, local de nascimento, sede, país, tema(s) principal(is), categoria taxonómica, género, autor, desporto, desenvolvedor, realizador, subclasse de, banhado por, compositor, empresa de produção, religião, pai.

Responda apenas com o nome da relação, sem explicações extras.

Fig. 1. Prompt 1: Zero-shot instruction prompt. The prompt instructs the model to identify the relation between two entities mentioned in a sentence, choosing from the set of relation types.

Leia a seguinte frase:
 "O escritor José Saramago nasceu em Azinhaga, Portugal."

Classifique a relação entre "José Saramago" e "Azinhaga" na frase.
 Explicação das relações possíveis:

- "género": obra ou artista e o seu género.
- "local de nascimento": uma pessoa e o local onde nasceu.
- "autor": obra literária e o seu criador.

Responda apenas com a relação correta, sem explicações extra.

Fig. 2. Prompt 2: Instruction with relation type descriptions. The example shows only three relation descriptions, with the remaining ones following a similar pattern.

relation types. The input to the model consisted of the original sentence with the two target entities explicitly marked using XML-style tags (`[SUBJ]entity[/SUBJ]` and `[OBJ]entity[/OBJ]`), enabling the model to localize the relevant context. The model was trained using cross-entropy loss and evaluated using classification metrics, with macro-averaged F1 as the primary metric. Macro F1 computes the unweighted mean of F1 scores across all classes, ensuring equal importance for each relation type. Given that the dataset is balanced across relation types, macro-averaging provides a suitable and fair basis for evaluation.

The training process used the train/test split explained in the section 2.1, with hyperparameters set according to standard BERT fine-tuning practices: a learning rate of $2e-5$, 5 epochs, and a train batch size of 8.

3 Results and Discussion

Table 2 presents the overall performance of the evaluated models, reporting precision, recall, and macro F1 scores for both prompting and fine-tuning.

Among the LLMs, gemma-3-27B-it combined with Prompt 2 achieved the best performance, reaching a macro F1 score of 0.89. This result suggests that larger instruction-tuned models can benefit from more descriptive prompting, potentially leveraging the added context to disambiguate fine-grained relations.

Mistral-7B also showed strong performance, particularly with Prompt 2, improving from 0.70 (Prompt 1) to 0.80. Interestingly, despite its larger size, Llama-

Model	Method	Precision	Recall	Macro F1
gemma-2-2b-it	Prompt 1	0.75	0.65	0.63
gemma-2-2b-it	Prompt 2	0.69	0.41	0.46
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Prompt 1	0.81	0.70	0.70
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Prompt 2	0.84	0.80	0.80
gemma-3-27b-it	Prompt 1	0.87	0.82	0.82
gemma-3-27b-it	Prompt 2	0.93	0.89	0.89
Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct	Prompt 1	0.89	0.84	0.83
Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct	Prompt 2	0.92	0.81	0.82
BERTimbau	Fine-tune	0.96	0.96	0.96

Table 2. RC results using different models and strategies

3.3-70B did not outperform gemma-3-27B and showed more stable performance across both prompts. The smaller gemma-2-2B showed limitations, especially with Prompt 2, indicating that smaller models may struggle to incorporate and reason over additional prompt context.

The fine-tuned BERTimbau model significantly outperformed all prompt-based methods, reaching a macro F1 of 0.96, confirming the effectiveness of supervised learning when sufficient labeled data is available. This highlights the potential of domain-specific fine-tuning for high-accuracy RC in low-resource languages like Portuguese.

Table 3 presents a comparative analysis of F1 scores per relation between the best-performing prompting configuration (gemma-3-27B-it with Prompt 2) and the fine-tuned BERTimbau model. The fine-tuned model achieves higher F1 scores across several relation types, particularly in cases where precise semantic disambiguation is required, such as *subclass of* and *instance of* with improvements of over 0.3 in F1. However, prompting remains competitive, especially for relations with more direct lexical cues, such as *father*, *place of birth*, and *director* where both methods perform equally well or with minimal differences. These results achieved by gemma-3-27B-it reinforce the notion that prompting with large generative models can yield impressive results in zero-shot settings, especially considering that the model is not exposed to any training data.

It is important to note that as generative LLMs increase in size, operating them becomes significantly more demanding, requiring high-end computational infrastructures or access through paid platforms. In this context, fine-tuning smaller, more computationally efficient models, such as BERTimbau with only 110M parameters, remains an attractive alternative for practical and resource-constrained NLP applications. This is especially relevant as studies continue to show that prompt-based methods still lag behind supervised fine-tuning with smaller models [12,16].

The high precision and recall achieved by the fine-tuned BERTimbau model, in particular, underscore its potential for contributing to reliable KG construction. Meanwhile, prompt-based generative approaches, despite slightly lower overall accuracy, offer a simpler and adaptable alternative, especially in scenarios where annotated data is scarce.

Relation	gemma-3-27b-it	BERTimbau
author	0.97	0.97
composer	0.97	0.98
country	0.93	0.97
developer	0.94	0.90
director	1.00	0.98
father	1.00	1.00
genre	0.81	0.94
headquarters location	0.98	0.98
instance of	0.57	0.89
located in or next to body of water	1.00	0.95
main subject	0.82	0.89
occupation	0.94	1.00
place of birth	1.00	1.00
production company	0.98	0.98
religion	0.64	0.98
sport	0.98	0.98
subclass of	0.71	0.84
taxon rank	0.84	0.95

Table 3. F1 scores per relation for the best prompting configuration (gemma-3-27b-it with Prompt 2) and fine-tuned BERTimbau model.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

In this work, we explored RC as a key step toward structured KG construction from Portuguese text. We investigated prompting strategies using generative LLMs, ranging from the smaller gemma2 model with 2 billion parameters to the larger Llama3.3 model with 70 billion parameters. In addition to prompting, we fine-tuned BERTimbau, a Portuguese BERT-based model on our custom dataset’s training set.

Despite having only 110 million parameters, BERTimbau outperformed the larger generative models, confirming the strength of supervised adaptation when labeled data is available. This highlights a practical trade-off: fine-tuning delivers superior accuracy, making it highly suitable for RC and thus reliable for a KG population pipeline, whereas prompting enables competitive performance without the need for a dedicated training process, based solely on inference.

As future work, we plan to integrate RC with entity recognition for a complete triple extraction process. We also intend to represent the extracted triples directly into KG structures, enabling a fully automated end-to-end pipeline from Portuguese text to structured knowledge.

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A Appendix: English Translations of Prompts

This appendix provides English translations of Prompt 1 and Prompt 2, presented in Figures 3 and 4, respectively.

```
Analyze the following sentence:
"The film Central do Brasil was directed by Walter Salles."

Identify the relation between "Central do Brasil" and "Walter Salles".
Choose only one of the following possible relations: instance of,
occupation, place of birth, headquarters location, country, main subject,
taxon rank, genre, author, sport, developer, director, subclass of,
located in or next to body of water, composer, production company,
religion, father.

Respond only with the relation name, with no additional explanations.
```

Fig. 3. Prompt 1: Zero-shot instruction prompt.

```
Read the following sentence:
"The writer José Saramago was born in Azinhaga, Portugal."

Classify the relation between "José Saramago" and "Azinhaga" in the
sentence.
Explanation of possible relations:
- "genre": artwork or artist and their genre.
- "place of birth": a person and their birthplace.
- "author": literary work and its creator.

Respond only with the correct relation, with no additional explanations.
```

Fig. 4. Prompt 2: Instruction with relation type descriptions.